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POWDER MICROSCOPICAL EVALUATION – INGREDIENTS OF *TRISAMA*

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Abstract

Background: The demand for herbal products is rising in the modern period, which subsequently drives up the need for raw materials. Adulteration and substitution are increasing along with manufacturing these days to make up for the need of raw materials. Therefore, it's critical to monitor this. Hence the pharmacognosy of raw material is very important. Powder microscopy is a component of pharmacognosy that aids in both medication authenticity and impurity detection. For the majority of preparations, powders are used frequently. In order to evaluate and standardize herbal powder and, eventually, authenticate herbal drugs, powder microscopy is a valuable tool. **Material & Method:** Powder microscopy of *Trisama* was carried out. *Trisama* is an ayurvedic formulation containing *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.) and *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.). Slides of each ingredient of *Trisama* were prepared using required reagents and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Trisama* shows Starch grains, vessel elements, tracheid, fibers, stone cells etc. **Discussion and Conclusion:** Structure like stone cells and trichome are indicating presence of *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.); Starch grains, Crystal fibre with prism etc. are indicating presence of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.); fragment of fibers with attached parenchyma and reticulated vessel, Cortical parenchyma embedding oleoresin cell etc. these structures are indicating presence of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.) in the *Trisama*.

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INTRODUCTION:

The usage of natural medications has increased recently on the international market. Herbal medications are employed extensively in all industries, including the pharmaceutical, cosmeceutical, nutraceutical, etc. Nowadays, pharmaceutical businesses and dealers frequently witness adulteration and substitution as a result of the increased demand for herbal medications. Therefore, pharmacognosy is crucial in ensuring optimal treatment efficacy and in keeping an eye on this. The simplest, most affordable, and easiest method for standardizing and authenticating herbal drugs is powder microscopy, which is a branch of pharmacognosy.

Using the precise herbal medications that are stated in the scriptures is crucial to achieving the highest level of therapeutic efficacy. It cannot accomplish the intended action if it is altered in any manner. Therefore, powder microscopy is crucial for identifying herbal drugs and detecting impurities. Here, for the present study *Trisama* is selected for the powder microscopy. *Trisama* is an important polyherbal formulation of the Ayurved.¹ It contains *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz., Family - Combrataceae), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd., Family - Menispermaceae) and *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc., Family - Zingiberaceae).

AIM:

To analyse the microscopic features in the powder of *Trisama*.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To assess the microscopic features in the powder of *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.) and *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.).
2. To compare the assessed features of herbal drugs with their standards mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Trisama was used for the powder microscopy. *Trisama* is an ayurvedic formulation containing *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.) and *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.). Fruits of *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.), stem of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.) and rhizomes of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.) were collected and powdered following the standard operating procedure.

Slide preparation:

Slides of each ingredient of *Trisama* were prepared separately using required reagents and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in authentic reference.²⁻⁴

Staining agents: Safranin and iodine

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:**Table No.01: Powder microscopic characters found in *Trisama***

No.	Microscopic characters	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Sunthi</i>
1.	Stone cells	+	-	-
2.	Crystal fiber	-	+	-
3.	Tracheids	-	+	-
4.	Prism	-	+	-
5.	Trichome	+	-	-
6.	Reticulate vessel with pigment cell (Vessel elements)	-	+	+
7.	Starch grains	-	+	+
8.	Fragment of fiber	-	-	+
9.	Oleoresin cell	-	-	+
10.	Fibers	+	+	+
11.	Parenchymatous tissue	-	-	+
12.	Crystals	-	-	+
13.	Cortical parenchyma embedding oleoresin cells and starch grains	-	-	+

Table No.02: Powder microscopic study of *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Haritaki</i>	Figure no.
1.	Fibers	Fig. 1
2.	Epidermis	Fig. 2
3.	Stone cells	Fig. 3
4.	Trichome	Fig. 4

Table No.03: Powder microscopic study of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Guduchi</i>	Figure no.
1.	Starch grains	Fig. 5
2.	Vessel elements	Fig. 6
3.	Tracheid	Fig. 7
4.	Fibers	Fig. 8
5.	Crystal fibre with prism	Fig. 9

Table No.04: Powder microscopic study of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Sunthi</i>	Figure no.
1.	Cork in surface view	Fig. 10
2.	Reticulated vessel with pigment cells	Fig. 11
3.	Fiber	Fig. 12
4.	Starch grains	Fig. 13
5.	Fragment of fibers with attached parenchyma and reticulated vessel	Fig. 14
6.	Cortical parenchyma embedding oleoresin cell and starch grains	Fig. 15

The current study provides knowledge on the microscopic characteristics of the herbal materials. The powder of *Trisama* was chosen for this microscopic investigation. Powder microscopy of *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.) shows, epidermis, fibers, stone cells, trichome. Powder microscopy of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.) shows, starch grains, vessel elements, crystal fiber, tracheid, fiber, prism. Powder microscopy of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.) shows, reticulated vessel, starch grain, fragment of fiber with attach parenchyma and reticulated vessel, cortical parenchyma embedding oleoresin cell and starch grains, cork in surface view, fragment of with attach parenchyma and reticulated vessel, reticulated vessel with pigment cell.

Standardizing Ayurvedic formulation is a challenging and intricate process. However, it's necessary to guarantee the efficacy and security of herbal medications, making them suitable for their use. Every powder component of *Trisama* was examined under microscope in the current investigation, and the microscopic characteristics of each were recorded. These characteristics could be useful for precisely identifying and spotting contaminants in materials that are available in market.

Powder microscopic study of *Haritaki (Terminalia chebula Retz.)*

Fig. 1

Fibers

Epidermis

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Stone cells

Trichomes

Fig. 4

Powder microscopic study of *Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia Willd.)*

Fig. 5

Starch grains

Vessel elements

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Tracheid

Fibers

Fig. 8

Crystal fibre with prism

Fig. 9

Powder microscopic study of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.)

Cork in surface view

Fig. 10

Reticulated vessel with pigment cells

Fig. 11

Fiber

Fig. 12

Starch grains

Fig. 13

Fragment of fibers with attached parenchyma and reticulated vessel

Fig. 14

Cortical parenchyma embedding oleoresin cell and starch grains

Fig. 15

CONCLUSION:

The current study's findings aid in the identification of herbal formulations like Trisama. Fibers, epidermis, stone cells and trichome these structures are indicating presence of *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.); starch grains, vessel elements, tracheid, fibers and crystal fibre with prism these structures are indicating presence of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.); Cork, reticulated vessel with pigment cells, fiber, starch grains, fragment of fibers with attached parenchyma and reticulated vessel, cortical parenchyma embedding oleoresin cell and starch grains these structures are indicating presence of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.) in the *Trisama*. In order to improve public health, powder microscopy of herbal drugs should be done prior to their introduction into pharmaceutical market.

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